

**Entrepreneurship thought to establish sport project among STAPS
 graduated Sports hall as a model
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ARTICLE INFORMATION	Abstract
<p>Original Research Paper Received: 13/01/2022 Accepted: 19/04/2022 Published: 01/06/2022</p> <p>Keywords: Entrepreneurship thought, Sport project, Graduated, Sciences and techniques Physical and sport activities</p>	<p>The Object of the study aims to defined the level of Entrepreneurship thought to among STAPS graduated; and to know what they know about establish project as sport hall and for this purpose we used descriptive method On a sample composed of 148 graduated from institute of sciences and techniques of physical and sport activities, and for data collection, we designed questionnaire, the data was analyzed using SPSS version 21, The results showed: 1-graduated have medium level in Entrepreneurship thought. 2-graduates have a medium level in knowledge about establishing small projects such as gym hole. 3- Graduates have a high level in knowledge about managing small projects such as gym hole. We recommended Adding sport entrepreneurship course in the formation of STAPS students.</p>
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1. Introduction:

Many countries followed a strategies that support youth and also are involved in the concept of Entrepreneurship, as you see the internship is considered to be now the key of development and achieving what we call sustainable development, the Algerian nation is trying to find drastic solutions to combat the unemployment phenomena through benefiting from other development countries experience and that by encouraging youth to do Entrepreneurship and having their own projects also Schumpeter(1934) says that Entrepreneurship is seen as new combinations including the doing of new things or the doing of things that are already being done in a new way. New combinations include (1) introduction of new good, (2) new method of production, (3) opening of a new market, (4) new source of supply, (5) new organizations. (Handayani, Rokhmani, Dwi Satrio, & Rachmawati, 2017)

According to H. Hannula and S. Pajari-Stylman (2008) Entrepreneurship is a wide concept. It means not only entrepreneurship as an entrepreneur. It means individual entrepreneurship, organizational entrepreneurship and entrepreneurship, as well. Kyrö and Carrier (2005) define these four issues in the following way:

1. The oldest form of individual, self-oriented entrepreneurship, meaning
2. The creation, management and ownership of a small enterprise, refer-
3. Corporate or organizational entrepreneurship referring to an organization's collective behavior (organizational entrepreneurship).
4. Entrepreneurship referring to the interplay between individual and Entrepreneurship is both creating and doing business and a way of working. (Sijde, Annemarie , Blaauw, & Diensberg, 2008)

Habitual entrepreneurs have five characteristics in common:

They passionately seek new opportunities. Habitual entrepreneurs stay alert, always looking for the chance to profit from change and disruption in the way business is done. Their greatest impact occurs when they create; entirely new business models. New business models revolutionize how revenues are made, costs are incurred, or operations are conducted, sometimes throughout an entire industry. One reason that the emergence of the Internet as a new medium of business has been accompanied by dizzyingly high company valuations is that investors perceive its potential to profitably transform virtually every aspect of economic life.

They pursue opportunities with enormous discipline. Habitual entrepreneurs not only are alert enough to spot opportunities, but make sure that they act on them. Most maintain some form of inventory, or register, of unexploited

opportunities. They make sure that they revisit their inventory of ideas often but they take action only when it is required. They make investments only if the competitive arena is attractive and the opportunity is ripe.

They pursue only the very best opportunities and avoid exhausting themselves and their organizations by chasing after every option. Even though many habitual entrepreneurs are wealthy, the most successful remain ruthlessly disciplined about limiting the number of projects they pursue. They go after a tightly controlled portfolio of opportunities in different stages of development. They tightly link their strategy with their choice of projects, rather than diluting their efforts too broadly.

They focus on execution—specifically, adaptive execution. Both words are important. People with an entrepreneurial mindset execute that is, they get on with it instead of analyzing new ideas to death. Yet they are also adaptive—able to change directions as the real opportunity, and the best way to exploit it, evolves.

They engage the energies of everyone in their domain. Habitual entrepreneurs involve many people—both inside and outside the organization—in their pursuit of an opportunity. They create and sustain networks of relationships rather than going it alone, making the most of the intellectual and other resources people have to offer and helping those people to achieve their goals as well. (McGrath & Ian, 2000)

In the other hand, the role of university is to activate and format an entrepreneur individual by excellence so that he will have possibilities if he wants to get in the world of Entrepreneurship, and also having an Entrepreneurship thought, as well as it allows them to depend on their selves and that's what really create a strong and development economy.

Entrepreneurship allows youth to open other doors instead of waiting for the turn, and also it is to be the best choice for the individuals that want to achieve wealth and can't work under bosses, but this needs developing Entrepreneurship thought studying in college

And in the sport field, there are a lot of options and directions that can an individual choose under the concept of Entrepreneurship such as being a personal trainer, open a gym, rehab facility or zumba dancing halls ...etc.

And this specialty includes a lot of courses and Curriculum that Ministry of Higher Education has set for the students To be taught in the goal of guidance to the field and the professional environment and which make him a capable individual in many ways, such as the private sector (entrepreneurship) We can mention the projects they aim to as opening a sport

hole, that requires a variety of capabilities to manage advertise and work for it. for that, our main goal here is to Our main goal here is to evaluate entrepreneurship thought in the sport field among individuals who were graduated from sciences and techniques of physical and sport activities (STAPS) institutes and there are few studies that have talked about sport entrepreneurship, for example the study of Cardella, Brizeida Raquel, & José (2021) that have carried out a comprehensive and systematic review of literature on entrepreneurship and sport as tools for implementing social change, The results showed the identification of six major recurring themes in the literature. For the purposes of our contribution, the recently developed line of research which considers sport as a tool for solving social problems through social change appears to be of particular importance.

Also María and others (2017) tried to understand what perceived capabilities, internal factors (entrepreneurial courses), and external factors (environment) influence entrepreneurial intentions of students of physical activity and sport sciences,

The study of Zeinab Mondalizadeh (2017) that purposed to determine the challenges of entrepreneurship in sport colleges in Iran and presenting reformation policies The result showed that the most important entrepreneurship challenges in sport colleges were status of sports entrepreneurial consulting services, present the programs of entrepreneurship training, the status of research and development unit, and innovation system in physical education colleges, the status of profitable from the research results and disproportion between educational contents and job skills. A survey of conflicts and challenges entrepreneurship in sport colleges emphasizes on long-term planning and attention for employing and using the safe planning by competence managers to provide background for entrepreneurship, innovation, and science production.

We can mention also the study of Hamidreza and others (2012) who also tried to examine the personality characteristics of students at the Islamic Azad University of Sari in 2011 academic year. The results revealed the fact that the clearness of thought among the female students was higher than that of the male and the dreaming aspect among the male students was higher than that of the females. Such factors of control centre, clearness of thought and pragmatism for graduate students were higher than those of the undergraduates.

at last the study of Nasip and others (2017) that purposed to to investigate the relationship between individual psychological characteristics

(i.e. innovativeness, locus of control, self-confidence, propensity to take risk, need for achievement and tolerance for ambiguity) and entrepreneurial intention. The results have shown that innovativeness, self-confidence, propensity to take risk, need for achievement and tolerance for ambiguity are positively related to entrepreneurial intention among undergraduate students. However, locus of control is not significantly related to entrepreneurial intention.

We absolutely believe the importance of this study appears in the lack of the local studies specially in Arabic And in the sport field. so we asked a principle questions:

What is the level of Entrepreneurship thought among STAPS graduated?

And also three secondary questions:

- **To what extend STAPS graduated individuals know about establishing a private project such as gym hole?**
- **To what extend STAPS graduated individuals know about managing a private project such as gym hole?**

2. Methods and Materials:

2.1. Participants

The participants of the study consist of 148 individuals graduated from STAPS institutes; they were randomly selected from the total population.

2.2. Materials

We designed questionnaire that contains 11 questions to evaluate entrepreneurial thought among graduates of STAPS institutes, after viewing literature background; The questions were organized into two dimensions² establishing (6 questions), management (5 questions). The answers to each item used a 3 Likert scale. Level, Questionnaire responses coded: Yes = 3 sort of = 2 no= 1.

2.3. Reliability and validity

Constrict Validity:

To achieve the validity of constrict for the questionnaire. The Coefficient of correlation was calculated between its sub-dimensions, and the results are in table 1.

Table 1: correlation between dimensions of questionnaire

	Creation	Management	total score
Creation	1	,470**	,856**
Management	,470**	1	,858**
total score	,856**	,858**	1

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The table shows that the correlation coefficients of each dimension and the total scores are statistically significant at (0.01) and (0.05), indicating a high degree of consistency of the questionnaire clauses and that they measure where they claim to be measuring.

Cronbach's Alpha reliability:

To achieve the reliability for the questionnaire. The Coefficient of Cronbach's Alpha was calculated, and the results are in table2.

Table 2: Cronbach's Alpha reliability for questionnaire and its sections

Dimensions	NUMBER OF questions	Cronbach's Alpha
creation and organization	1-6	,856
Management	7-11	,853
total score	1-11	,870

The reliability index for the whole questionnaire was 0.870 and all components also showed high indexes (0.853-0.856). This means that the tool is characterized by high stability.

2.4. Design and Procedure

After viewing literature background, we design questionnaire, we made sure of its clarity by passing it to judges for evaluation, it was approved to be given as a questionnaire for an exploratory sample of 33 graduates of STAPS institutes to calculate the reliability and validity, we kept the number of questions as it is 11 question, to be distributed on a sample of 170 graduates, but only counting 148 questionnaires and exclude the rest for not answering some parts.

2.5. Statistical Analysis

The data was analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) for Windows (version 21), The data was analyzed by employing Mean, Standard Deviation, and Relative importance for each statement.

3. Results

- **Q1: To what extend STAPS graduated individuals know about establishing a private project such as gym hole?**

To determine how much graduated from STAPS know about establishing small projects, Means, Standard Deviation and Relative importance were calculated for each statement of second dimension.

Table 3 : Means, Standard Deviations and Relative importance

	Statements	N	Mean	S.D	RII	Level
01	Do you know people who had an experience in opening sports hall	148	2,31	0,89	77,24	H
02	Have you ever prepared a budget scheme for the establishment of a sports hall	148	1,37	0,74	45,94	M
03	Do you have an idea of regulatory laws that talks about establishing a sports hall	148	1,54	0,76	51,34	M
04	Do you have an idea of social partnerships (health insurance, ...) and their relationship with sports halls	148	1,52	0,76	50,89	H
05	Do you have an idea how to manage a sports hall	148	2,18	0,74	72,96	H
06	Do you have an idea of periodic contributions to the users of sports halls	148	1,93	0,88	64,63	M
Total		148	1,80	0,795	60,50	M

The dimension consists of sixth statements to know what extend STAPS graduated individuals know about establishing a private project such as gym hole. The first statement asked about: “Do you know people who had an experience in opening sports hall” the result showed that mean was (M=2,31, SD=0,89) with relative importance index (RII =77,24) so the feedback for question was in the high level. The second statement about “Have you ever prepared a budget scheme for the establishment of a sports hall”, the result showed that mean was (M=1,37, SD=0,74) with relative importance index (RII=45,94) so the feedback for question was in the medium level, for the third statement “Do you have an idea of regulatory laws that talks about establishing a sports hall”, the result showed that mean was (M=1,54, SD=0,76) with relative importance index (RII =51,34) so the feedback for question was in the high level, the statement number four “Do you have an

idea of social partnerships (health insurance, ...) and their relationship with sports halls” the result showed that mean was ($M=1,52$, $SD=0,76$) with relative importance index ($RII=50,98$), so the feedback for question was in the high level, The last statement “Do you have an idea how to manage a sports hall”, the result showed that mean was ($M=2,18$, $SD=0,74$) with relative importance index ($IIR=72,96$) so the feedback for question was in the high level. The last statement “Do you have an idea how to manage a sports hall”, the result showed that mean was ($M=1,93$, $SD=0,88$) with relative importance index ($IIR=64,63$) so the feedback for question was in the high level.

The overall mean for managing small projects for graduated is ($M=1,80$), and the standard deviation is ($SD=0,75$); and with relative importance index ($IIR=60,50$), the respondents indicate that graduate well-informed about establishing small projects.

And we observed also that there were three statements at the high level, and the rest were in the medium level, the first highest RII were obtained by statements “Do you know people who had an experience in opening sports hall” with $RII=77,24$.

Figure 1: Means and the standard deviation of the establishing a small project

- **Q2: To what extent STAPS graduated individuals know about managing a private project such as gym hole?**

To determine how much graduated from STAPS know about managing small projects, Means, Standard Deviation and Relative importance were calculated for each statement of second dimension.

Table 4: Means, Standard Deviations and Relative importance

		N	Mean	S.D	RII	level
01	Do you have an idea for the best brands and coded sports equipment?	148	2,07	0,73	69,13	H
02	Do u have any idea which are the best brands and the good the rated sport equipment?	148	1,93	0,88	64,63	M
03	Do you have an idea about regular subscriptions for gym users?	148	2,07	,73	69,13	H
04	Do you have an idea of how to make a profit out of sports hall?	148	2,16	,73	72,28	H
05	Do you have some ideas that go with the sports hall and make a profit	148	2,25	,77	75,21	H
Total		148	2,10	0,77	70,08	H

The dimension consists of five statements to know what extend STAPS graduated individuals know about managing a private project such as gym hole, the first statement asked about: “Do you have an idea for the best brands and coded sports equipment” the result showed that mean was (M=2,07, ST=0,73) with relative importance index (RII=69,14) so the feedback for question was in the high level. The second statement about Do u have any idea which are the best brands and the good the rated sport equipment?, the result showed that mean was (M=1,94, SD=0,88) with relative importance index (RII=64,63) so the feedback foe question was in the medium level, for the third statement “Do you have an idea about regular subscriptions for gym users?”, the result showed that mean was (M=2,07, SD=0,73) with relative importance index (RII=69,14) so the feedback for question was in the high level, the statement number 4 “Do you have an idea of how to make a profit out of sports hall?” the result showed that mean was (M=2,17, SD=0,73) with relative importance index (RII=72,28), so the feedback for question was in the high level The last statement “Do you have some ideas that go with the sports hall and make a profit”, the result showed

that mean was ($M=2,26$, $SD=0,77$) with relative importance index ($RII=75,22$) so the feedback for question was in the high level.

The overall mean for managing small projects for graduated is ($M=2,10$), and the standard deviation is ($SD=0,77$); and with relative importance index ($IIR=75,22$), the respondents indicate that graduate well-informed about managing small projects. And we observed also that there were 4 statements at the high level, and the rest was in the low level, the first highest RII were obtained by statements “Do you have some ideas that go with the sports hall and make a profit” with $RII=75.22$.

Figure 1: Means and the standard deviation of the managing a small project

4. Discussion

The first Research question was posed: To what extend STAPS graduated individuals know about establishing a private project such as gym hole. the table 3 shows the means, SD and RII and we find that four statements were at the high level and based on the RII of each statement, and the overall relative importance index for establishing small projects for graduated is ($IIR=60,50$), so it indicates that graduates have a medium level in knowledge about establishing small projects such as gym hole.

The second Research question was posed: To what extent STAPS graduated individuals know about managing a private project such as gym hole. the table 4 shows the means, SD and RII and we find that five statements were at the high level and based on the RII of each statement, and the overall relative importance index for managing small projects for graduated is (IIR=70,08), so it indicates that graduates have a high level in knowledge about managing small projects.

The overall relative importance index for the small projects among graduated is (IIR=65,65), And we observed also that there were 7 statements at the high level, and the rest was in the medium level, indicate that graduated have medium level in Entrepreneurship thought.

That may be due to the fact that they didn't get the formation that allows them to have entrepreneurship thought. So according to the course approved by the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research, students of STAPS institutes do not include any courses that define entrepreneurship for students, the same goes for other courses, it does not include any axis that serves to develop or direct the student's thinking to go to the private sector and try to establish a private project.

We can also say, the students' lack of interest in entrepreneurship may also be due to their unwillingness to take risks, especially since the project of opening a gym hole requires an acceptable amount of money, as they do not meet the conditions of a successful entrepreneur. Especially the formation of an individual who is capable of succeeding in private projects requires a special formation.

Also, they don't know about the programs that state has established to support these small projects, nor the administrative procedures. And according to Maria and others (2017) Entrepreneurial capacities to create enterprises and become entrepreneurs should be promoted to encourage the entrepreneurial spirit among students of physical activity and sport sciences. Therefore, university education as a component of policies to promote entrepreneurship will increase the number of entrepreneurs in the sports industry. So the previous studies as Nasip and others (2017), Maria and others (2017) confirmed the necessity of developing students in the entrepreneurship.

5. Conclusion:

To eliminate unemployment, we must encourage entrepreneurship in the sports field, based on awareness and training of students to engage in small projects, according to the level of entrepreneurial thought among graduates of STAPS institutes it is medium, here we give some recommendations:

- Adding sport entrepreneurship course in the formation of STAPS students.
- Giving attention in the next studies to entrepreneurship in sport based on the current study.
- Incorporate the sport entrepreneurship in the thought among students of STAPS.
- We recommend studying the topic of sport entrepreneurship more in the future.

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